

Kinetics of Acid-catalysed Resorcinol-Formaldehyde Reaction

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A kinetic study of the reaction of resorcinol with formaldehyde has been carried out at temperatures 65, 70, 75 and 80° using hydrochloric acid as catalyst. The pH was maintained at 2.15, 2.38, 2.75 and 3.20. The rate is found to increase with the decrease in pH of the reaction. The reaction follows an overall second order rate kinetics. The overall rate constant has been resolved into the step rate constants. The Arrhenius parameters for the overall reaction and also for the step reactions have been calculated. A comparative study of the overall second order rate constant for resorcinol-formaldehyde reaction has been made with those of overall second order rate constant for phenol-formaldehyde and *p*-cresol-formaldehyde reaction in order to establish the effect of substituents on the rate of the reaction.

PHENOLS combine with aldehydes to give linear or crosslinked products of high molecular weight. Because of the vast applications of these products, a comprehensive kinetic study of these reactions is likely to reveal information regarding the factors controlling the nature and properties of these products.

The kinetics of the acid catalysed reaction of phenols with formaldehyde have been the subject of several studies¹⁻¹². A review of the literature reveals that the kinetics of acid catalysed resorcinol-formaldehyde reaction have so far not been investigated. In the present paper, acid catalysed resorcinol-formaldehyde reaction has been carried out at temperature 65, 70, 75 and 80° and at pH 2.15, 2.38, 2.75 and 3.20.

Experimental

Materials and method :

Resorcinol (E. Merck) was further purified by recrystallisation. Formalin (37.5%, formaldehyde), potassium iodide, potassium bromate, sodium thio-sulphate, iodine used were B.D.H. products. Sodium bisulphite (J. T. Baker) was used for the estimation of formaldehyde. Hydrochloric acid and methanol were A.R./C.P. quality, and *p*-nitroaniline (Thomas Baker & Co.) was used for the preparation of indicator. A German NBE thermostat ($\pm 0.05^\circ$) was used for rate studies.

Resorcinol solution (0.897 *M*) was prepared by using methanol-water mixture (1 : 1, v/v). Reaction mixture containing calculated amounts of resorcinol, formaldehyde and hydrochloric acid, preheated to the desired temperature was placed in a round bottom flask fitted with a water condenser. The flask was suspended in the thermostat bath and aliquots of the reaction mixture were withdrawn

at different time intervals and placed in an ice-bath to freeze the reaction. Formaldehyde was determined by Ripper's sodium bisulphite method as well as by hydroxylamine hydrochloride method, and resorcinol was determined spectrophotometrically using diazotised *p*-nitroaniline as indicator.

Preparation of diazotised *p*-nitroaniline indicator :

p-Nitroaniline solution (0.5%) was prepared in 2 *N* HCl. This solution was diazotised (5 ml) by adding 5% aqueous sodium nitrite solution (0.5 ml) to give the required indicator. Every time a fresh sample of the indicator was used. To nearly 10^{-5} *M* resorcinol solution (0.5 ml) were added gum accacia (1 ml), 50% sodium acetate solution (1 ml) and freshly prepared diazotised *p*-nitroaniline (1 ml). After 1 min, a 20% solution of anhydrous sodium carbonate (2 ml) was added and diluted to 10 ml. Optical density of this solution was recorded and its exact concentration was determined from standard curve, drawn by using known concentrations of resorcinol.

Results and Discussion

Results of kinetic studies carried out at various temperature and pH are given in Table 1. Acid catalysed resorcinol-formaldehyde reaction proceeds according to the equations,

The overall second order rate expression for the formation of products is

$$\frac{dx}{dt} = k(a-x)(b-y) \quad (1)$$

TABLE 1—RESULTS OF KINETIC STUDY

Initial [Resorcinol] = 0.39 M						
pH	Initial [HOHO] M	Time s	[HOHO] mol dm ⁻³	[Resorcinol] mol dm ⁻³	Second order rate constant dm ³ mol ⁻¹ s ⁻¹	Average second order rate constant dm ³ mol ⁻¹ s ⁻¹
Temp. = 65°						
2.15	0.4303	3600	0.3309	0.2135	4.47 × 10 ⁻⁴	(4.74 ± 0.24) × 10 ⁻⁴
		6000	0.2876	0.1413	4.93 × 10 ⁻⁴	
		8400	0.2686	0.1038	4.83 × 10 ⁻⁴	
2.38	0.4043	5400	0.3465	0.2875	1.51 × 10 ⁻⁴	(1.56 ± 0.04) × 10 ⁻⁴
		7800	0.3267	0.2515	1.55 × 10 ⁻⁴	
		10200	0.3079	0.2219	1.61 × 10 ⁻⁴	
2.75	0.4295	12600	0.2863	0.1821	1.58 × 10 ⁻⁴	(4.28 ± 0.28) × 10 ⁻⁵
		7200	0.4059	0.3480	4.36 × 10 ⁻⁵	
		10300	0.3939	0.3279	3.90 × 10 ⁻⁵	
3.20	0.3628	14400	0.3806	0.3039	4.29 × 10 ⁻⁵	(8.22 ± 0.50) × 10 ⁻⁵
		18800	0.3658	0.2776	4.58 × 10 ⁻⁵	
		9000	0.3575	0.3807	7.47 × 10 ⁻⁵	
		12600	0.3545	0.3755	8.37 × 10 ⁻⁵	
		16200	0.3520	0.3711	8.56 × 10 ⁻⁵	
		19800	0.3498	0.3674	8.48 × 10 ⁻⁵	
Temp. = 70°						
2.15	0.4152	2400	0.3145	0.2128	7.06 × 10 ⁻⁴	(6.98 ± 0.06) × 10 ⁻⁴
		4200	0.2780	0.1485	6.93 × 10 ⁻⁴	
		6000	0.2525	0.1049	6.97 × 10 ⁻⁴	
2.38	0.3912	3600	0.3159	0.2587	3.27 × 10 ⁻⁴	(3.58 ± 0.41) × 10 ⁻⁴
		5400	0.2934	0.2186	3.20 × 10 ⁻⁴	
		7200	0.2615	0.1622	3.84 × 10 ⁻⁴	
2.75	0.4145	9000	0.2456	0.1305	3.99 × 10 ⁻⁴	(8.49 ± 0.52) × 10 ⁻⁵
		5700	0.3728	0.3170	9.26 × 10 ⁻⁵	
		8700	0.3607	0.2961	8.22 × 10 ⁻⁵	
3.20	0.4031	11700	0.3472	0.2729	8.07 × 10 ⁻⁵	(9.23 ± 0.14) × 10 ⁻⁵
		14700	0.3332	0.2465	8.44 × 10 ⁻⁵	
		9000	0.3959	0.3774	9.38 × 10 ⁻⁵	
		12000	0.3936	0.3732	9.20 × 10 ⁻⁵	
		15000	0.3914	0.3696	9.10 × 10 ⁻⁵	
		18000	0.3890	0.3654	9.23 × 10 ⁻⁵	
Temp. = 75°						
2.15	0.3926	1800	0.2774	0.1882	1.25 × 10 ⁻³	(1.32 ± 0.21) × 10 ⁻³
		3000	0.2499	0.1371	1.15 × 10 ⁻³	
		4200	0.2107	0.0686	1.56 × 10 ⁻³	
2.38	0.3772	2400	0.2836	0.2253	7.02 × 10 ⁻⁴	(7.08 ± 0.12) × 10 ⁻⁴
		4200	0.2477	0.1590	7.20 × 10 ⁻⁴	
		6000	0.2235	0.1179	7.16 × 10 ⁻⁴	
2.75	0.4060	7800	0.2070	0.0926	6.94 × 10 ⁻⁴	(2.07 ± 0.11) × 10 ⁻⁴
		3600	0.3508	0.2938	2.01 × 10 ⁻⁴	
		5400	0.3278	0.2520	2.08 × 10 ⁻⁴	
3.20	0.4213	7200	0.3168	0.2336	2.22 × 10 ⁻⁴	(2.36 ± 0.15) × 10 ⁻⁵
		9000	0.3023	0.2082	1.98 × 10 ⁻⁴	
		5400	0.3938	0.3685	2.52 × 10 ⁻⁵	
		7200	0.3903	0.3622	2.48 × 10 ⁻⁵	
		9000	0.3879	0.3585	2.25 × 10 ⁻⁵	
		10800	0.3853	0.3535	2.21 × 10 ⁻⁵	
Temp. = 80°						
2.15	0.3826	900	0.2534	0.1652	3.11 × 10 ⁻³	(3.20 ± 0.34) × 10 ⁻³
		1500	0.2250	0.1115	2.94 × 10 ⁻³	
		2100	0.1935	0.0583	3.60 × 10 ⁻³	
2.38	0.4137	1800	0.3010	0.1913	1.13 × 10 ⁻³	(1.16 ± 0.15) × 10 ⁻³
		2700	0.2825	0.1602	0.97 × 10 ⁻³	
		3600	0.2505	0.1028	1.20 × 10 ⁻³	
2.75	0.3823	4500	0.2325	0.0669	1.35 × 10 ⁻³	(5.45 ± 0.38) × 10 ⁻⁴
		2700	0.2986	0.2407	5.32 × 10 ⁻⁴	
		4500	0.2721	0.1952	4.84 × 10 ⁻⁴	
3.20	0.4301	6300	0.2416	0.1426	5.23 × 10 ⁻⁴	(3.72 ± 0.47) × 10 ⁻⁵
		8100	0.2158	0.0946	5.41 × 10 ⁻⁴	
		3600	0.4156	0.3646	4.47 × 10 ⁻⁵	
		5400	0.4139	0.3597	3.53 × 10 ⁻⁵	
		7200	0.4084	0.3517	3.48 × 10 ⁻⁵	
		9000	0.4030	0.3418	3.60 × 10 ⁻⁵	

where, a and b are the initial concentrations of resorcinol and formaldehyde, respectively, x and y are the respective amounts of resorcinol and formaldehyde reacted at time t .

It is obvious from equations (A) and (B) that resorcinol is being used in both the steps. Therefore, at any stage in the reaction, the amount of the resorcinol consumed will be more than that of formaldehyde. This can be verified from Table 1. The average proportion of resorcinol and formaldehyde reacted was actually found to be

$$x \approx 1.77y \quad (2)$$

Substituting the value of x in equation (1) and on integration one gets

$$k = \frac{2.303 \times 1.77}{t(1.77b - a)} \log \frac{a}{b} \left(\frac{b-y}{a-1.77y} \right) \quad (3)$$

Acid catalysed resorcinol-formaldehyde reaction obeys an overall second order rate law. A linear dependence of $\log a/b (b-y/a-1.77y)$ on time (Fig. 1) further illustrates this point.

Fig. 1. Plot of $\log a/b \left(\frac{b-y}{a-1.77y} \right)$ vs time at temp. $65 \pm 0.05^\circ$ and pH 3.2.

By plotting $\log k/T$ vs $1/T$ (Fig. 2), the values of Arrhenius parameters and entropy of activation for the overall reaction and also for the step reactions (A) and (B) have been calculated. These values have been summarised in Table 2. As pH increases, the activation energy increases, confirming that the reaction is catalysed by H^+ . This is further established from the fact that a linear plot is obtained when $\log k$ is plotted against pH (Fig. 3).

Fig. 2. Plot of $\log k/T$ vs $1/T$ at pH=2.98: (O) k , (Δ) k_1 and ($\bullet$) k_2 .

Fig. 3. Plot of $\log k$ vs pH at temp. $70 \pm 0.05^\circ$.

TABLE 2—ARRHENIUS PARAMETERS FOR RESORCINOL-FORMALDEHYDE REACTION

pH	Overall reaction		Step reaction (A)		Step reaction (B)	
	ΔE kcal mol ⁻¹	$\log A$ dm ³ mol ⁻¹ s ⁻¹	ΔE_1 kcal mol ⁻¹	$\log A_1$ dm ³ mol ⁻¹ s ⁻¹	ΔE_2 kcal mol ⁻¹	$\log A_2$ dm ³ mol ⁻¹ s ⁻¹
2.15	22.87	7.13	24.31	10.66	19.59	7.50
2.38	35.92	16.34	32.89	15.48	35.98	18.09
2.75	51.66	26.80	47.72	23.60	50.72	27.99
3.20	61.01	33.09	58.32	29.79	62.05	35.12

Due to the strong *ortho* and *para* directing influence of phenolic hydroxyl group, the reactivity of the phenol depends upon the number of *ortho* and *para* positions available for the reaction. Besides, presence of a substituent affects the orientation of an entering methylol group and causes activation or deactivation of the parent phenol.

Comparative study of the overall rate constants for resorcinol formaldehyde reaction has been made with phenol-formaldehyde¹⁰ and *p*-cresol-formaldehyde¹¹ reaction at similar conditions of temperature and pH. The rate is found maximum in case of resorcinol-formaldehyde reaction and minimum in *p*-cresol-formaldehyde reaction: Resorcinol-HCHO > Phenol-HCHO > *p*-Cresol-HCHO. In resorcinol, the presence of a hydroxyl group *meta* to the phenolic hydroxyl group strongly activates the resorcinolate ion making *ortho* and *para* positions of the resorcinolate ion highly susceptible to the attack of the electrophile. The rate is, therefore, expected to be higher in comparison to phenol. In *p*-cresol, the methyl group being *ortho-para* directing and located *meta* to the reaction sites, the reactivity of *p*-cresol would be less towards the addition of formaldehyde as compared to phenol.

Calculation of stepwise rate constants: From reactions (A) and (B), the rate of formation of monomethylol resorcinol is

$$\frac{dy}{dt} = k_1(na - y - r)(b - y) \quad (4)$$

where, (a-x), (b-y) and (y-r) are the concentrations of resorcinol, formaldehyde and monomethylol resorcinol, respectively at time t, and x, y and r are the respective amounts of resorcinol, formaldehyde and monomethylol resorcinol reacted at time t, and n is the functionality of resorcinol.

The rate of formation of tetrahydroxydiphenylmethane is

$$\frac{dr}{dt} = k_2(na - y - r)(y - r) \quad (5)$$

where, (na - y - r) is the concentration of resorcinol at time t.

The amount of resorcinol reacted at any stage of the reaction is equal to the sum of the amount of formaldehyde and monomethylol resorcinol reacted at time t,

$$-\frac{dx}{dt} = -\frac{dy}{dt} - \frac{dr}{dt} \quad (6)$$

Therefore, from equations (4), (5) and (6),

$$-\frac{dx}{dt} = -nk_1(a-x)(b-y) - nk_2(a-x)(y-r) \quad (7)$$

It follows from equations (1) and (7),

$$k(a-x)(b-y) = nk_1(a-x)(b-y) + nk_2(a-x)(y-r) \quad (8)$$

$$k = nk_1 + nk_2 \frac{(y-r)}{(b-y)} \quad (9)$$

Now $r = x - y$, and the functionality of resorcinol, $n = 1$,

$$k = k_1 + k_2 \left(\frac{2y-x}{b-y} \right) \quad (10)$$

Substituting the values of x, y and k (Table 1) at two time intervals, two simultaneous equations for k_1 and k_2 at a given temperature and pH were obtained. These equations were then solved for k_1 and k_2 . The average values of k_1 and k_2 thus obtained at various temperature and pH are given in Table 3.

TABLE 3—STEP RATE CONSTANTS AT DIFFERENT pH VALUES AND TEMPERATURES

Temp. °C	pH	Step rate constant $\text{dm}^3 \text{mol}^{-1} \text{s}^{-1}$		k_2/k_1
		k_1	k_2	
65	2.15	1.74×10^{-4}	2.83×10^{-3}	16.20
	2.38	7.69×10^{-4}	1.36×10^{-2}	17.65
	2.75	2.89×10^{-3}	5.39×10^{-2}	18.50
70	3.20	7.31×10^{-3}	1.38×10^{-1}	18.15
	2.15	2.48×10^{-4}	4.05×10^{-3}	16.40
	2.38	1.39×10^{-4}	2.29×10^{-3}	17.80
	2.75	4.86×10^{-3}	8.80×10^{-2}	18.70
75	3.20	8.21×10^{-3}	1.51×10^{-1}	18.30
	2.15	3.98×10^{-4}	6.55×10^{-3}	16.40
	2.38	2.30×10^{-4}	3.75×10^{-3}	16.30
80	2.75	1.00×10^{-4}	1.79×10^{-3}	17.90
	3.20	1.99×10^{-3}	3.82×10^{-2}	18.99
	2.15	7.95×10^{-4}	1.05×10^{-2}	17.70
	2.38	5.10×10^{-4}	6.10×10^{-3}	16.40
	2.75	1.99×10^{-4}	3.15×10^{-3}	16.11
	3.20	2.95×10^{-3}	5.17×10^{-2}	17.50

As can be seen from Table 3, the rate of formation of tetrahydroxydiphenylmethane is 16-19 times the rate of formation of monomethylol phenol, i.e. $k_2/k_1 \approx 16-19$

An attempt was also made to evaluate the ratio k_2/k_1 from purely theoretical considerations. From equations (4) and (5) one obtains

$$\frac{d(y+r)}{dt} = k_1(b-y)(na-y-r) + k_2(y-r)(na-y-r) \quad (11)$$

On dividing equation (11) by (7)

$$\frac{d(y+r)}{dx} = \frac{k_1(b-y)(na-y-r) + k_2(b-y)(na-y-r)}{nk_1(a-x)(b-y) + nk_2(a-x)(b-y)} \quad (12)$$

or

$$\frac{d(y+r)}{dx} = \frac{(na-y-r)}{n(a-x)} \quad (13)$$

On integration,

$$\log(na-y-r) = \frac{1}{n} \log(a-x) + \log c \quad (14)$$

Putting the conditions at $t=0, y=0$ and $r=0$, $\log c = \log na^{(n-1)/n}$

Putting the value of $\log c$ in equation (14),

$$\log (na - y - r) = \frac{1}{n} \log (a - x) + \log na^{(n-1)/n} \quad (15)$$

$$\text{or } (y+r) = na - na^{(n-1)/n} (a-x)^{1/n} \quad (16)$$

To determine the ratio between reacted resorcinol to formaldehyde, equation (5) is subtracted from (4),

$$\frac{d(y-r)}{dt} = k_1(b-y)(na-y-r) - k_2(y-r)(na-y-r) \quad (17)$$

Dividing equation (17) by equation (4) yields,

$$\frac{d(y-r)}{dy} = 1 - \frac{k_2}{k_1} \frac{(y-r)}{(b-y)} \quad (18)$$

$$\text{or } \frac{d(y-r)}{dy} = 1 - u \frac{(y-r)}{(b-y)} \quad (19)$$

where, $u = k_2/k_1$, and upon integration, one gets,

$$\frac{(y-r)}{(b-y)^u} = -\frac{1}{1-u} \frac{1}{(b-y)^{u-1}} + C \quad (20)$$

Putting the conditions at $t=0$, $y=0$ and $r=0$

$$C = \frac{1}{1-u} \cdot b^{1-u}$$

Putting the value of this constant in equation (21), one gets,

$$(y-r) = \frac{1}{u-1} \cdot (b-y) - \frac{1}{u-1} (b-y)^u \cdot b^{1-u} \quad (21)$$

By adding equation (16) and (22), one obtains,

$$2y = na - na^{(n-1)/n} (a-x)^{1/n} + \frac{1}{u-1} (b-y) - \frac{1}{u-1} \cdot b^{1-u} \cdot (b-y)^u \quad (22)$$

This is solved for x ,

$$x = a - \left[\frac{a^{1-n/n}}{n} \left\{ na - 2y + \frac{1}{u-1} (b-y) - \frac{1}{u-1} \cdot b^{1-u} (b-y)^u \right\} \right]^n \quad (23)$$

u can be obtained from equation (23) by knowing the amount of x and y at a given time interval. We have calculated u at temperature $65 \pm 0.5^\circ$ and at pH 2.15 and 2.38, and these values are reported in Table 4. The relation ($x=1.77y$) has nowhere been used in determining the value of k_2/k_1 . The ratio k_2/k_1 given in Table 3 involves indirectly the fact, $x=1.77y$. The average values of k_2/k_1 in Table 3 are in good agreement with the values in Table 4. This confirms that the approximation used in obtaining the second order rate expression (3), regarding the proportions of resorcinol and formaldehyde is very much in order. This has further been confirmed by making a comparison of the values of the overall rate constant obtained using equation (3) with the overall rate constant values as obtained purely from the theoretical consideration of the reaction, i.e. substituting the value of $(y-r)$ from equation (21)

TABLE 4—CALCULATED VALUES OF $k_2/k_1 = u$

Temp. = 65°		Calculated values of $k_2/k_1 = u$	Average value of u
pH	Time s		
2.15	3600	16.10	16.30
	6000	16.60	
	8400	16.20	
2.38	5400	18.90	17.65
	7800	16.60	
	10200	16.30	
	12600	18.70	

in the overall rate expression (8), which gives,

$$k(b-y) = k_1(b-y) + \frac{k_2}{u-1} [(b-y) - b^{1-u}(b-y)^u]$$

$$k = k_1 + \frac{k_2}{u-1} \left[1 - \left(\frac{b-y}{b} \right)^{u-1} \right] \quad (24)$$

From equation (24) and utilising the values of the step rate constants at temperatures 65 and 70° , and at pH 2.15 and 2.38 from Table 3, the values of the overall rate constants have been calculated. These are given in Table 5 along with the values obtained from equation (3). From Table 5, it is confirmed that the values of the overall rate constants for the acid catalysed resorcinol-formaldehyde reaction reported by us are in order.

TABLE 5—COMPARISON OF OVERALL RATE CONSTANTS

Temp. $^\circ\text{C}$	pH	Average value of overall rate constant $\text{dm}^3 \text{mol}^{-1} \text{s}^{-1}$	
		From eqn. (3)	From eqn. (24)
65	2.15	0.44×10^{-3}	0.35×10^{-3}
	2.38	0.32×10^{-3}	0.27×10^{-3}

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